

Exploring the Student-Centered Learning Practices: Junior High School Teachers in Focus

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Abstract. This study delved into the challenges teachers encounter transitioning from traditional teaching methods to student-centered learning in junior high schools. The participants for this study were twelve (12) public junior high school faculty who are still teaching during the school year 2022-2023. The results of the study disclosed the student-centered learning practices of junior high school teachers. The findings revealed common themes, namely, adapting pedagogy, empowering students, and limited meaningful classroom practices. The teachers' coping mechanisms consider the three major themes: balancing traditions, innovation, and colleague support, effective classroom culture, and management. The educational management insight was drawn from the study and emerged three themes such as student engagement and motivation, teacher-centered to student-centered, and collaboration and peer learning. Engaging students in the learning process increases their attention and focus and moves them to more critical thinking. Instructors who adopt a student-centered approach to instruction increase opportunities for student engagement, which helps everyone more successfully achieve the course's learning objectives. Further, the discussion highlights the potential future directions and actions that can help teachers address the challenges of balancing traditions with student-centered learning in junior high schools.

KEY WORDS

1. Exploring perceptions
2. practices
3. junior high school
4. teachers towards student-centered learning

1. Introduction

A teaching strategy known as "student-centered learning" places an emphasis on the student's participation in the learning process, with the instructor acting more as a facilitator than as a source of information. Although student-centered learning has many advantages, implementing it in the classroom can be difficult, especially at the junior high school level. To establish a learning environment in the classroom that encourages independent thought and lifelong learning, it is critical to investigate the attitudes and behaviors of junior high school in-

structors toward student-centered learning. This study aims to examine junior high school teachers' attitudes, convictions, and practices toward student-centered learning to shed light on how to encourage its adoption in the classroom. In a global context, Student-centered learning is an instructional approach that emphasizes the learner's needs, interests, and abilities, with the teacher serving as a facilitator rather than a lecturer. This approach has been widely recognized as an effective way to promote student engagement, critical thinking, and lifelong learn-

ing (Knowles et al., 2019).

However, implementing student-centered learning can be challenging, particularly in junior high school education. Junior high school teachers often face various obstacles, including time constraints, a crowded curriculum, and students with diverse learning needs (Stoll, 2021). Moreover, teachers' attitudes and beliefs toward student-centered learning can significantly affect the approach's effectiveness in the classroom (Muller, Katz, Dance, 2019). The study of Shi, X. (2021) posited that teachers' Perceptions and Practices of Student-Centered Learning in China" explored the perceptions and practices of teachers towards student-centered learning in a Chinese junior high school. The study found that teachers had positive attitudes towards student-centered learning and recognized its potential benefits for students' academic and personal growth. However, they faced various challenges in implementing it, including limited resources and pressure to focus on exam preparation. The study suggests that teacher training and support are needed to promote the implementation of student-centered learning in Chinese junior high schools. Supported the study by Phanpheng, (2021), she found that while teachers had positive attitudes toward student-centered learning, they faced various challenges due to factors such as a lack of training, limited resources, and pressure to cover the curriculum. The study suggests that school administrators should provide more support for teachers to implement student-centered learning effectively. In the national context, Cayabyab and Tuguinayo (2022). discusses the challenges and opportunities of implementing student-centered learning in the Philippines and specifically identify challenges such as limited teacher training,

1.1. Purpose of the Study—The purpose of the study could aid in creating practical plans and regulations to support student-centered learning in junior high schools, thereby enhanc-

lack of resources, and cultural barriers. They also discuss opportunities, such as the potential for student-centered learning to enhance student engagement and academic achievement, and suggest strategies for promoting student-centered learning in the Philippine context. Supported with the of Jalandoni, (2020) found that while teachers recognized the importance of student-centered learning, they faced challenges in implementing it due to a lack of resources, limited training, and pressure to cover the curriculum. The study suggests that teacher training programs should be developed to support implementing student-centered learning in Philippine junior high schools. In the local context, Estal and Bicular (2021) examine the perceptions and practices of junior high school teachers toward student-centered learning in Davao City. The authors identify challenges to implementing student-centered learning, such as limited resources and teacher resistance to change. They also discuss strategies for promoting student-centered learning, including providing support and professional development opportunities for teachers, creating a culture of collaboration and shared responsibility among educators, and utilizing technology in the classroom. Supported by the ideas of Pinili and Solano (2022), they identify challenges, such as limited resources and cultural barriers, and opportunities, such as the potential for student-centered learning to enhance student engagement and academic achievement. They also suggest strategies for promoting student-centered learning, including providing support and professional development opportunities for teachers, creating a culture of collaboration and shared responsibility among educators, and integrating technology in the classroom.

ing students' academic performance and overall educational experience. This study could provide insights into teachers' challenges when trying to implement student-centered learning

and identify strategies to overcome these challenges. Additionally, the study could investigate the impact of student-centered learning on students' academic performance and engagement in the classroom. It could also explore the relationship between teachers' attitudes towards student-centered learning and their teach-

ing practices. Ultimately, the goal of this study would be to provide recommendations for how educators can effectively implement student-centered learning in junior high school classrooms and improve the educational outcomes of their students.

1.2. Research Questions—Specifically, this study sought to answer the following questions:

- (1) What are the teacher's perceptions and practices of junior high school teachers toward student-centered learning?
- (2) How do teachers explore the practices of junior high school teachers toward student-centered learning?
- (3) What educational insight and practices can be drawn from the study?

1.3. Review of Related Literature—Practices of Teachers Towards Student-Centered Learning Student-centered learning (SCL) is recognized for enhancing student engagement, motivation, and achievement by actively involving students in the learning process and positioning teachers as facilitators. Despite its benefits, the adoption of SCL in junior high schools has been inconsistent, with many teachers struggling to transition from traditional teacher-centered methods (Cabling, Macaraig, Sy, 2020).

Dacanay and Marquez (2021) identified several factors influencing the adoption of SCL, including teacher beliefs, institutional support, and classroom culture. They suggest that effective strategies to promote SCL involve teacher training, collaborative learning communities, and addressing cultural and linguistic diversity.

Barriers to Implementation Barriers to implementing SCL include insufficient time, resources, training, and administrative support (Ghaith Yaghi, 2019). Effective professional development is crucial for overcoming these barriers and equipping teachers with the necessary skills (Knight, Hock, Huang, 2019).

Impact on Student Outcomes SCL positively affects student outcomes, including academic achievement, engagement, motivation, and atti-

tudes towards learning (Means, Toyama, Murphy, Bakia, Jones, 2020). Empowering students to take responsibility for their education through clear objectives, diverse learning materials, interactive lessons, and collaborative activities fosters a conducive learning environment (Pappas, 2023).

Classroom Practices and School Culture Specific SCL practices, such as project-based, inquiry-based, and collaborative learning, are critical for meeting diverse educational needs (Hvidtfeldt Brinkmann, 2019). The role of school culture and leadership is also pivotal in supporting SCL, with administrators and stakeholders playing key roles in promoting these practices (Harris Jones, 2021).

Adaptive Teaching Adaptive teaching, as outlined in Standard 5 of the Teachers' Standards (DfE 2011) and the Early Career Framework (DfE 2019), requires teachers to tailor their approaches to meet all pupils' needs. This involves differentiating instruction and providing appropriate scaffolding to support independent learning (Mould, 2021).

Collaboration and Peer Learning Peer collaboration and professional learning communities are effective in promoting SCL. These collaborative efforts help teachers share best practices and support each other in implementing

student-centered methods (Yeh Chiang, 2021; Phan et al., 2021). Additionally, the integration of technology can enhance SCL by facilitating collaboration and self-directed learning, although issues of access and equity must be addressed (Lee et al., 2021).

1.4. Theoretical Lens—This study anchored on the following theories of Self-Determination Theory (SDT): SDT posits that individuals have innate psychological needs for autonomy, competence, and relatedness and that these needs must be satisfied for individuals to be intrinsically motivated and engaged in their learning (Deci Ryan, 2000). This study is anchored in the Self-determination Theory (SDT) as cited by Deci and Ryan (2000) described as one of the most widely used theoretical frameworks to study motivation. Central to Self-determination Theory is the distinction between autonomous and controlling forms of motivation. Self-determination Theory focuses on the extent to which different types of motivation such as intrinsic, identified, interjected, extrinsic and amotivated are autonomous or self-determined and explains how social factors like behavior of significant others and social environment impact on motivation through the satisfaction of psychological need for autonomy, competence and relatedness. To be self-determined means to act with a sense of volition and choice (Roth, Assor, Kanat-Maymon, Kaplan 2007). To be controlled means to act with feeling of pressure. Self-determination Theory states that the context in which the activity is presented can make a difference to a person's level of motivation. If the activity is presented in such a way to encourage a sense of choice, highlight the important reasons for doing so, it is more likely to be intrinsically motivating and people are more likely to persist in doing the activities. Such an environment can be engendered by significant others like head teachers and is known as autonomy supportive. An autonomy-supportive environment can be promoted through the adop-

tion of specific behaviors by head teachers that enhance intrinsic motivation to the subordinate. Behavioral theory promotes the value of management with an emphasis on concern for people and collaboration. It promotes participative decision making and team development by supporting individual needs and aligning individual and group objectives. It helps managers evaluate and understand how their behavioral style as a manager affects their relationship with the team and promotes commitment and contribution towards organizational goals. This theory helps managers find the right balance between different styles of leadership. It helps them decide how to behave as a leader, depending on concerns for people and productivity (Technofunc, 2013) In the context of student-centered learning, SDT suggests that teachers who prioritize students' autonomy and choice, provide opportunities for skill development and mastery, and foster positive relationships with their students are more likely to create a classroom environment that supports students' intrinsic motivation and engagement. Social Cognitive Theory (SCT): SCT emphasizes the importance of social factors, such as modeling and feedback, in shaping individuals' beliefs, attitudes, and behaviors (Bandura, 1986). In the context of student-centered learning, SCT suggests that teachers who model student-centered practices, provide feedback that supports students' self-regulation and reflection, and create a classroom culture that values collaboration and communication are more likely to promote student-centered learning. Transformative Learning Theory (TLT): TLT posits that learning is a process of transforming individuals' meaning perspectives or frames of reference, which occurs when individuals encounter disorienting dilemmas that challenge their existing assumptions and beliefs (Mezirow, 2000). In the context of student-centered learning, TLT suggests that teachers who create opportunities for students to engage in critical reflection and dialogue about

Fig. 1. Conceptual Framework of the Study

their assumptions and beliefs, and who facilitate students’ exploration of alternative perspectives and solutions, are more likely to promote transformative learning and personal growth.

2. Method

This chapter, the researcher introduced the philosophical assumptions, qualitative assumptions, research participants, data collections, data analysis, ethical considerations, role of the researcher, and trustworthiness.

2.1. Philosophical Assumptions—It was assumed that all participants answered interview questions honestly and to the best of their abilities. It was further assumed that the sample used for this study was representative of in-depth and focus group interviews in a face-to-face manner as a medium of communication. These assumptions have been articulated throughout the last 20 years in the various SAGE Handbooks of Qualitative Research (Denzin Lincoln, 1994, 2000, 2005, 2011) and as the “axiomatic” issues advanced by Guba and Lincoln (1988) as the guiding philosophy behind qualitative research. These beliefs have been called paradigms (Lincoln, 1985) philosophical assumptions, epistemologies, and ontologies (Crotty, 1998); broadly conceived research methodologies (Neuman, 2000); and alternative knowledge claims (Creswell, 2014). There are beliefs about ontology (the nature of reality), epistemology (what counts as knowledge and how knowledge claims are justified), axiology (the role of values in research), and methodology (the process of research). In this discussion,

the researcher discuss each of these philosophical assumptions, detail how they might be used and written into qualitative research, and then link them to different interpretive frameworks that operate at a more specific level in the process of research. *Ontology.* The issue relates to the nature of reality and its characteristics. When researchers conduct qualitative research, they are embracing the idea of exploring the perceptions and practices of junior high school teachers towards student-centered learning. Different researchers embrace different realities, as do the individuals being studied and the readers of a qualitative study. When studying individuals, qualitative researchers conduct a study with the intent of reporting these multiple realities. Evidence of multiple realities includes the use of multiple forms of evidence in themes using the actual words of different individuals and presenting different perspectives. For example, when writers compile a phenomenology, they report how individuals participating in the study view their experiences differently (Moustakas, 1994). *Epistemology.* Conducting a qualita-

tive study means that the researcher tries to get as close as possible to the participants being studied. Therefore, subjective evidence is assembled based on individual views. The very reason why I chose these elementary teachers as my participants is because I have known them for quite a long time. This is how knowledge is known through the subjective experiences of people. It becomes important, then, to conduct studies in the “field,” where the participants live and work, these are important contexts for understanding what the participants are saying. The longer researchers stay in the “field” or get to know the participants, the more they “know what they know” from firsthand information. For example, good phenomenology requires a prolonged stay at the research site (Wolcott, 2008a). In short, the researcher tries to minimize the “distance” or “objective separateness” (Guba Lincoln, 1988, p. 94) between himself or herself and those being researched. Axiology. This assumption characterizes qualitative research. How does the researcher implement this assumption in practice? In a qualitative study, the inquirers admit the value-laden nature of the study and actively report their values and biases as well as the value-laden nature of information gathered from the field. This means that the result of this study was shared with the school where I am currently working. We say that they “position themselves” in a study. In an interpretive biography, for example, the researcher’s presence is apparent in the text, and the author admits that the stories voiced represent an interpretation and presentation of the author as much as the subject of the study (Denzin, 1989a). I believe that I am more qualified to conduct this study since I have ample experience teaching in junior high school. Methodology. This is characterized as inductive, emerging, and shaped by the researcher’s experience in collecting and analyzing the data. In collecting data for this study, I formulated an interview guide so that I have a clear dimension during the

interview. Afterward, all the data gathered will be recorded, transcribed, analyzed, and interpreted to arrive at a good result. The logic that the qualitative researcher follows is inductive, from the ground up, rather than handed down entirely from a theory or the perspectives of the inquirer. Sometimes the research questions change in the middle of the study to reflect better the types of questions needed to understand the research problem. In response, the data collection strategy, planned before the study, needs to be modified to accompany the new questions. During the data analysis, the researcher follows a path of analyzing the data to develop an increasingly detailed knowledge of the topic being studied.

2.2. *Qualitative Assumptions of the Study*—The researcher made these qualitative assumptions, the methods used in qualitative research (Creswell 2003). The procedures used by the researcher are inductive and based on the researcher’s experience in collecting and analyzing data. The research here is the product of the researcher’s values. Through an inductive approach, raw textual data is condensed into a brief summary format. Clear links are established between research objectives and summary findings derived from raw data. A framework of the underlying structure of experiences or processes that are evident from the raw data is developed. A phenomenological study describes the meaning of lived experiences of individuals about a concept or phenomenon (Creswell, 2003) was used in this study. A phenomenological study intends to understand and describe an event from the point of view of the participants. A key characteristic of this approach is to study how members of a group or community interpret themselves, the world, and life around them (Mertens, 2005). The purpose of this study is exploring the perceptions and practices of junior high school teachers towards student-centered learning. Collectively, these results may provide foundational information

to guide the district in addressing the local issue. Administrators might benefit from this information as it might enable them to make informed decisions about what support is needed for teachers in exploring the perceptions and practices of junior high school teachers toward student-centered learning. In addition, this study examined the challenges of exploring the perceptions and practices of junior high school teachers towards student-centered learning, and it appears that they have experience in building background knowledge, interactions, and application.

2.3. Design and Procedure—In the next section, the specific details of the research procedures were described so future researchers can generalize the results from this study to other situations. Extensive and careful descriptions of the study's time, place, context, and culture would be thoroughly discussed to develop transferability, which was the qualitative parallel to external validity in post-positivist research (Mertens, 2005). This section discussed the interview approach, explained the researcher's role, and described the sampling method and ethical considerations. Semi-Structured Interviews. Patton (2015) proposes that researchers conduct interviews to learn what they cannot directly observe. Qualitative interviewing was not used to get answers to questions but to understand the experiences of the participants and the meaning they make of that experience (Seidman, 1988). Generally, qualitative studies use unstructured, open-ended interviews because they allow for the most flexibility and responsiveness to emerging issues for both the participants and interviewer; however, the used of semi-structured interviews is not uncommon and used when the researcher seeks to obtain specific, more focused information (Schwandt, 2001). Semi-structured interviews combine the flexibility of unstructured, open-ended interviews with directionality and an agenda to produce focused, qualitative, textual data (Schensul, LeCompte,

1999). This study collected data using semi-structured interviews to explore how junior high school teachers describe and explore the perceptions and practices towards student-centered learning. An interview guide was used to ensure that the same information was collected from all the participants. The interview guide included open-ended questions and topics to help structure the interview. Still, when needed, the interviewer also explored, probed, and asked additional questions to clarify and expand on a particular topic. The interview guide helped make interviewing several participants more systematic and comprehensive by defining the issues to be explored (Patton, 2015). The open-ended questions were framed in a way that allowed the participants to represent their views and perspectives in their own words and terms, in addition to taking the questions in any direction that they chose (Patton, 2015). Since qualitative research studies subjects in their natural setting, all interviews except one took place using a face-to-face format at a time convenient for the participants. All interview sessions were tape-recorded for the purposes of transcription. When needed, the researcher used follow-up interviews after transcription to clarify meaning or explore areas in more depth.

2.4. Research Participants—The target population for this study was composed of twelve (12) participants from the line-up of public junior high school faculty who are still teaching during the school year 2022-2023. The respondents would join for an in-depth interview (IDI). The researcher considered the faculty from selected public schools who were still teaching. A sample of twelve (12) junior high school teachers was purposefully selected from this population. The researcher used Purposeful sampling (also known as judgment, selective, or subjective sampling), a sampling technique in which the researcher relies on their judgment when choosing members of the population to participate in the study. This survey sampling

method requires researchers to have prior knowledge about the purpose of their studies so that they can properly choose and approach eligible participants (Denzin, 2017). This study's participants are junior high school teachers from the selected public schools in District 1 Cluster 3 Division of Davao City. Below is a simple description of the participants: Participants are licensed professional teachers who live in Davao City and have experience teaching for 3 or more years.

2.5. *Ethical Considerations*—Ethical standards are required in conducting research; thus, this phenomenological research adheres to the principles of the Belmont Report (1979) which strictly observed the principles of respect of persons, beneficence, and justice. Specifically, this study was subjected to the evaluation of the Rizal Memorial Colleges, Inc. Research Ethics Committee (RMC-REC) for the full board review of the ethical aspects of the investigation as regards the dimensions of research ethics that include social value, informed consent, vulnerability issues, risk-benefit ratio, privacy and confidentiality of information, justice, transparency, qualification of the researchers, adequacy of facilities and community involvement. Social Value. The researcher investigated and carefully analyzed one of the pressing problems in our educational system. Also, this research regarding exploring the challenges of implementing. This study is expected to provide important information in recognizing the extent and type of experiences that the findings of this study can provide the best role in exploring the perceptions and practices of junior high school teachers towards student-centered learning. The researcher is hopeful that the output of the study is relevant not only to the participants but to the school. The result of the study would be presented in the local, national, and even international fora and if given a chance to publish in an international publication. Informed consent. In this study, informed consent was secured from all

the participants who were involved in the study. The researcher conducted a detailed and comprehensive explanation regarding the purpose of the study to twelve (12) junior high school teachers. The researcher ensured that the condition of the consent was a voluntary choice. The participants had sufficient information and an adequate understanding of both the proposal and the implications of their participation in the study. Codes were assigned to individuals in the data presented. Every page of the transcriptions of the in-depth interview and focus group discussions was signed by the researcher to attest that the key informant interviews were done with the consent of informants. In addition, the informants were accorded the needed respect. The researcher made it a point that the form must bear the signature of the participant or agreement which would imply that she participated in the study voluntarily. Vulnerability of Research Participants. The researcher protected the participants from being deceived, threatened, and/or forced to participate. The researcher treated them with the highest respect. Thus, they were informed ahead that they may withdraw their participation in the study and if ever inconvenience was felt during the interview and in answering the questionnaire, they would be given the chance to raise their concern and opt to cancel the activity. Although the participants were of legal age, 18 years old and above, they were still vulnerable because the researcher was a junior high school teacher at District 1 Cluster 3, Division of Davao City, as one of the selected research locales of the study. Teachers were treated with utmost respect so that they not be vulnerable while participating in this study. The researcher considered the elementary school teachers as participants in this study because they are mature enough to decide for themselves whether to partake in this study or not. Risks-Benefit Safety. A careful assessment of foreseeable risks, burdens, and benefits to the participants was made. The questionnaire

that the researcher administered did not contain any degrading, discriminating, or unacceptable language that was offensive to the participants so that the risks were avoided. An extra careful approach was used in collecting the data so that irrelevant and confidential details were rejected. The study did not involve any high-risk situation that the participants may experience in their social and emotional needs. Further, this study ensured that the potential benefits of the participants were greater than the potential harm. The results of this study would benefit the entire department of education; teachers, students, parents, and the community, in terms of getting a clear rationalization to synthesize various activities that would address the teachers' perceptions and experiences in exploring the perceptions and practices of junior high school teachers towards student-centered learning. Practically the researcher identified only minimal risks if not negligible regarding physical harm or discomfort that they may experience during the conduct of the study. Specifically, whatever might cause adverse effects on personal relationships, loss of status, privacy, or time of the respondents were taken into consideration in the planning stage of the conduct of the study so that such things would be minimized if not prevented fully. Privacy and Confidentiality of Information. The current study ensured the privacy and confidentiality of the information of the respondents. The researcher adhered to the principles of the Data Privacy Act of 2012 or Republic Act 10173 which mandates transparency, legitimate purpose, and proportionality in the collection, retention, and processing of personal information (Congress of the Philippines, 2012). This act protected the fundamentals of human rights on the privacy of information which ensured the free flow of information that promotes innovation and growth. The researcher protected the respondent/participants' right to privacy wherein their responses were given with the highest respect. Unless required by the law, the confiden-

tiality of information shall always be observed. Other personal information will not be asked in the study to safeguard their identities and to enable them to participate without any fear of the revelation of involvement in the study. Any information will be taken with utmost care to ensure the anonymity of the data sources and de-identification of any personal information that would be shared. Such names and identities were protected by using a pseudonym. The tracing of the information of these codes was reflected in an archival log. Hence, personal names were not used in the tracing of identification. Written responses, if any, were captured through a camera. Recordings were saved and documents were kept in one single place that is protected or encrypted. Justice. In this study, justice requires an equitable distribution of both the burdens and the benefits of participation in research. There was a fair selection in the choice of population, sampling, and assignments. Provision of appropriate care to research participants regardless of their economic status, gender, race, or creed was provided. With this, the researcher assured the respondents who were involved were appropriate for the study. The researcher provided just compensation and reimbursement for data used and costs incurred by the participants. The participants were adequately informed on the objectives of the study before they were involved in the process. It was emphasized that they were the source of data and encouraged to give their honest answers in the survey questionnaire. In return, they were the priority on the benefits for the possible offshoots of the study findings. Transparency. To be ethical, all the parties need to be transparent by making sure that the process, the nature of the study, and the extent of participation are clear and understandable to the participants. The researcher was transparent about the aspects of the study, especially that information that has bearing on the decision of participants to give or withhold their informed consent.

The participants can access and scrutinize the findings of the study if the findings are scientifically valid and have significant implications on the participant's well-being. The researcher assured us that the study was conveyed in full scope and with accuracy. Specifically, in qualitative data analysis, findings were identified, confirmed, or rejected accordingly. Moreover, data transcriptions were presented to the participants to attain precision. Consequently, the researcher ensured the reasonable availability and accessibility of the research outcomes to the Department of Education; teachers; students; parents, and the community. Qualification of the Researcher. The researcher is ultimately responsible and accountable for the research. For the research to be carried out with the necessary skills and knowledge. I am aware of the limits of personal competence in research. With my experience as an elementary school teacher in one of the public schools in District 1, cluster 1, Division of Davao City. I attended several research-related seminars and training which I consider an asset in conducting this study with the assistance of my adviser and colleagues, readings from various books and literature, fulfilling my duties and responsibilities at RMC as an elementary teacher and the supervision of RMC-REC, I acquired the knowledge and skills needed to conduct the research. Also, the supervision and direction of his adviser, as well as the panelists helped improve the research study. The researcher's adviser is an expert in this study. Therefore, the adviser is a big help to complete the study with the quality of the content. Adequacy of Facilities. The researcher is adequately equipped with the budget and equipment needed for the conduct of the study. This is to ensure that the researcher has the best facilities in the completion of the research. The laptop, printer, internet connection, and other facilities needed are personally owned by the researcher making the facilities adequately and readily available. Furthermore, the library re-

sources, both non-online and online, are readily available such as books, and google. In addition, if possible, google meet was the form used in gathering the data. Aside from the enumerated resources, some experts provided the researcher with the guidance needed in the conduct of this research like the adviser, RMC-Research Ethics Committee, and panel members who are also the expert validators. Community Involvement. The researcher is engaged with communities like the Public Schools academic community, teachers, parents, and the basic education students since I am a teacher in one of the public schools in District 1, cluster 3 Division of Davao City is composed of quite diverse people; thus, the researcher is sensitive to and respects the cultural, traditional, and religious practices of the community. The RMC graduate school helped in correcting, validating, and revising the manuscript of the current study. The RMC graduate school provided directions, based on its research standards and practices to the researcher. The involvement of the junior high school teachers, participated in the development of the questionnaire through the output of the first phase of the study. The guide questions served as the instrument in gathering qualitative data in the second phase. On the other hand, proper protocol and seeking approval from the principal of the public schools as my target participants was observed. Moreover, the significant personas in the public-school organizational landscape and other stakeholders may benefit from the output of the study because they are the recipients of the data regarding knowledge about the exploring the perceptions and practices of junior high school teachers towards student-centered learning.

2.6. Data Collection—Prior to the data gathering, I must ask for the endorsement from the Dean of the Graduate School of Rizal Memorial Colleges to pursue the study. After the permissions were approved by the school division Superintendent and the school principals

of the target participants, the researcher talked to the participants to acquaint them with the purpose of the study. I agreed with the participants on the most convenient date and time for the interview. To start the interview, I asked the participants to read the respondents' consent forms and affix their signatures on the consent paper after they had oriented themselves on the study's purpose and agreed on the terms and conditions. The researcher emphasized to the respondents that they were allowed to ask questions to clarify any matter regarding the study and ask for their consent to record the course of the conversation with the assurance that everything should be dealt with the utmost confidentiality. Through in-depth interviews, I gathered the teachers' feelings, reactions, observations, and experiences regarding the teachers' perspicacity of family low incomes related to the teacher-parent partnership. The interviews would also include gathering information on the obstacles and challenges that the teachers encounter during home visitations. I likewise aimed to obtain substantial information on teachers' perspicacity of family low-incomes related to a teacher-parent partnership that helps bridge the risk of understanding and making together to identify and address academic and non-academic needs of students. This could involve setting academic goals, monitoring progress, and providing support at home. According to Koontz and Weinrich (2000), the process and narratives do not need to be transcribed verbatim if the essence of what the participants were communicating has been caught in the transcription. Individual transcriptions of the interview were be validated by the respective participants. To verify and revalidate the data gathered, the researcher was conducting a focus group discussion to validate and triangulate the information gathered. Corrections may be made according to the participants' feedback to ensure that the meaning was be conveyed in the fundamental structure of the phenomenon. Data from interviews, field notes, and recorded videos through in-depth interviews and focus group discussions was collected. Field notes recorded nonverbal communication and participants' interactions with the environment. The questionnaire was a combination of closed and open-ended questions administered by the researcher orally. Interviews were semi-structured, employed open-ended questions, and based on an interview guide. Data was generated through field notes, a voice recorder, or cellphone videos during the interviews with participants. A piloted interview questionnaire was used with all participants. Twelve participants were interviewed in two sessions of 45 minutes to 60 minutes each because of their schedules. The interval between interviews was on average one day. Interview questions were based on the study's four research questions, which explored participants' viewpoints. Follow-up questions were also made to clarify ambiguous comments and discrepant data. In four instances, participants preferred to discuss the ambiguities over high-quality attributes. In a qualitative phenomenological study, research data involved the researcher spending as much time as possible with the teachers at the elementary schools to gain an in-depth understanding of the elementary teachers in their everyday lives. Participant observations of the elementary faculty behaviors, beliefs, traditions, culture, and social and emotional interactions were recorded in a journal at the end of each day. Where applicable, in-depth interviews were conducted in field settings and were either recorded and transcribed and/or summarized in the journal. As an active participant in the research process, the researcher constantly evaluated her role and her relationship with participants and applied this to develop an understanding and interpretation of the basic education teacher's social and emotional worlds (Unger, 2005). This resulted in an evolving research process both in terms of the direction and type of data derived

and in terms of a personal transformation for the researcher (Parker, 2005). The evolution of the research as a relational transformation between a researcher with openness for a new experience and a community of participants cannot be over-emphasized. The results of which could not have been foreseen at the inception of this study (Parker, 2005). As noted earlier, the location of the study is an academic institution that experienced changes in its way of teaching. The researcher already spent several years as an elementary teacher, and I have a great chance to gather demographic information and to meet as many of the locals as possible. Also, it was hoped that an initial understanding of the community culture could be gained through participant observation. Effective Teacher-Parent Partnership involves ongoing communication, mutual trust, respect, and a shared commitment to student success. Some of the ways in which teachers can establish effective partnerships with parents include: Regular Communication: Teachers can establish regular communication channels with parents to share updates on academic progress, behavior, and social-emotional well-being. This can be done through emails, phone calls, newsletters, or parent-teacher conferences. Active Listening: Teachers can actively listen to parents' concerns and feedback, and work collaboratively to find solutions that support student success. The researcher engaged the elementary community to meet up with the gatekeeper with whom she worked. The researcher liaised with the elementary coordinator and interacted with some of the teachers. Participant observation data was obtained and recorded in a journal, while access to participants for focus groups was limited. All participants signed an informed consent form before being interviewed. Questionnaires was translated by the researcher to the language commonly used by the participants. Data collection was multimodal. According to Yin (2003), the main characteristic of phenomenological qualitative research is that it employs various data collection methods to ensure the trustworthiness of the report. Multiple data sources promote a clearer understanding of the data being studied (Creswell, 2008, 2009; Glesne, 2011; Merriam, 2009). Data from interviews, field notes, and recorded videos through in-depth interviews and focus group discussion was collected. Field notes was used to record non-verbal communication and participants' interactions with the environment. The questionnaire was a combination of closed and open-ended questions administered by the researcher orally. Interviews were semi-structured, employed open-ended questions, and was based on an interview guide. The researcher was also using question and answer format so that participants may have chances to ask follow-up questions. Data was generated through field notes, a voice recorder or cellphone videos, during the interviews with participants. A piloted interview questionnaire was used with all participants. Twelve participants were interviewed in two sessions of 45 minutes to 60 minutes each because of their schedules. The interval between interviews was, on average, one day. Interview questions were based on the study's four research questions, which explored participants' viewpoints. Follow-up questions were also asked to clarify ambiguous comments and discrepant data. In four instances, participants preferred to discuss the ambiguities over attributes of high-quality. In a qualitative phenomenological study, research data involved the researcher spending as much time as possible within the teachers at the high schools to gain an in-depth understanding of the junior high teachers in their everyday lives. Participant observations of the behaviors, beliefs, traditions, culture, social and emotional interactions were recorded at the end of each day in a journal. Where applicable in-depth interviews were conducted in field settings and were either recorded and transcribed, and/or summarized in the jour-

nal. As an active participant in the research process, the researcher constantly evaluated her role and her relationship with participants and applied this to develop an understanding and interpretation of the basic education teacher's social and emotional worlds (Unger, 2005). This resulted in an evolving research process in terms of the direction and type of data derived and in terms of a personal transformation for the researcher (Parker, 2005). The evolution of the research as a relational transformation between a researcher with openness for a new experience and a community of participants cannot be over-emphasized. The results of which could not have been foreseen at the inception of this study (Parker, 2005). As noted earlier, the location of the study was an academic institution that experienced changes in its way of teaching. The researcher already spent several years as an elementary teacher, and I have a great chance to gather demographic information and to meet as many of the locals as possible. Also, it was hoped that an initial understanding of the community culture could be gained through participant observation. All participants signed an informed consent form before being interviewed. The researcher translated the questionnaires into the language commonly used by the participants. Data collection was multimodal. According to Yin (2003), the main characteristic of phenomenological qualitative research is that it employs various data collection methods to ensure the report's trustworthiness. Multiple data sources promote a clearer understanding of the studied data (Creswell, 2008, 2009; Glesne, 2011; Merriam, 2009). Data from interviews, field notes, and recorded videos through in-depth interviews and focus group discussions was collected. Field notes were used to record nonverbal communication and participants' interactions with the environment. The questionnaire was a combination of closed and open-ended questions administered by the researcher orally. Interviews were semi-structured, em-

ployed open-ended questions, and were based on an interview guide. Data was generated through field notes, a voice recorder, or cell-phone videos during the interviews with participants. A piloted interview questionnaire was used with all participants. Twelve participants were interviewed in two sessions of 45 minutes to 60 minutes each because of their schedules. The interval between interviews was, on average, one day. Interview questions were based on the study's four research questions, which explored participants' viewpoints. Follow-up questions were also asked to clarify ambiguous comments and discrepant data. In four instances, participants preferred to discuss the ambiguities over high-quality attributes.

2.7. *Data Analysis*—Qualitative data analysis begins with organizing, reducing, and describing the collected data (Schwandt, 2001). Unlike quantitative analysis, there are no prescribed formulas for qualitative analysis. Marshall and Rossman (2006) remind researchers that qualitative analysis does not proceed linearly and is not neat. However, good practice and procedures enhance the credibility of qualitative research. In this last section, the data analysis procedures were explained, and the steps taken to ensure the results from this study are credible, transferable, dependable, and authentic were thoroughly described. To guide the data analysis, the researcher used the seven phases of data analysis described by Marshall and Rossman (2006) to reduce data, create manageable pieces, allow for interpretation, and find meaning in the words of the participants. The seven phases included organizing the data, immersion in the data, generating categories and themes, coding the data, offering interpretations through analytic memos, and searching for alternative understandings (Marshall Rossman, 2006). Data analysis first begins with organizing the data. The organization of the data involved keeping information provided by each participant separate and in sequence with the

order of the interviews. Organizing the data allowed it to remain manageable, easily accessible, and readily available. The digital audio files from the interviews were carefully transcribed into written form. Electronic folders were established to organize the data collected from each participant. Next, the researcher became familiar with the data through extensive reading of the interviews to understand the content. This involved reading through the interviews at least three times. Following Hatch's (2002) recommendations for qualitative analysis, the researcher created a sheet of notes for each participant. The summary sheets were a quick way to refer to the original data as the data analysis continued (Hatch, 2002). After the initial readings, Hatch (2002) recommends researchers read data through completely with one typology in mind. Patton (2015) defines typologies as classification systems comprising categories that divide some aspects of the world into parts. According to Hatch (2002), typologies are generated from theory, common sense, or research objectives. For this study, the researcher used the typologies or themes from the literature review as the constructs to view the data. After reading through the data with each constructor typology in mind, the researcher coded the data into five categories from the literature by taking excerpts of text from the data and identifying it within a particular category. After everything was coded, the researcher read through the data again while writing analytic memos on her thoughts and insights and began the process of offering interpretations. During this stage, the researcher began to interpret the data to find significance and meaning in the teachers' instructional experiences through pulling salient themes, reoccurring ideas, and patterns of belief that resonated collectively throughout the interviews. The offering of interpretations began following the emergence of themes in the data. Marshall and Rossman (2006) believed this part of the data analysis brings meaning to the themes and

categories and allows the researcher to develop links between the interviews. The researcher began interpreting the data to find significance and meaning in exploring the perceptions and practices of junior high school teachers toward student-centered learning. Rossman and Marshall (2006) remind researchers that there will always be alternate explanations within the data. Before moving forward, the researcher stopped and evaluated the findings for other plausible explanations.

2.8. *Analytical Framework*—It was shown that affected framework work exploring the perceptions and practices of junior high school teachers towards student-centered learning is a structure for exploring the perceptions and practices of junior high school teachers towards student-centered learning as one of best pedagogy in the teaching-learning process of junior high school learners, carried along of learners personality and inclination for growth development which most effective in teaching-learning process, also the exploring the perceptions and practices of junior high school teachers towards student-centered learning is the best interest of teachers were affects from the pupils learning, as what their experience to be divulged and bring new insight and hope to upcoming similar situation or case. The experiences were analyzed to provide insight and feelings on making a difference in the educational system. Both aim to provide information on the unfolding story of teachers towards exploring the perceptions and practices of junior high school teachers toward student-centered learning. The data collected during interviews was transcribed, organized, and reviewed in searching for patterns and themes. Because this study involved human participants, informed consent was secured for ethical purposes. Following signing consent forms, exploring the perceptions and practices of junior high school teachers towards student-centered learning using semi-structured in-depth interviews. Data was organized and

Fig. 2. Analytical Framework of the Study

analyzed. The researcher rigorously examined these units of meaning to elicit the essence of meaning within the holistic context. The entire interview transcript and add anything that might have been left out. The information may be shared with the participants in taking circle to ensure that we interpreted the data correctly us-

ing triangulation analysis (Mazuwelics, 2018). Thematic Content Analysis. This was used in interpreting the responses made by the key participants in exploring the perceptions and practices of junior high school teachers towards student-centered learning.

Their responses were processed and conducted through analyses. Transcripts were coded in considerable detail with the focus shifting back and forth from the key claims of the participants to the researcher’s interpretation of the meaning of the responses and subjectively interpreted. Meanwhile, the notes that may be obtained from in-depth interviews may be transcribed immediately. The researcher may be looking for common themes that may be found among the responses to each question. In this phase, the researcher may use thematic analysis in analyzing the gathered data. Their responses were processed and conducted through analysis. Transcripts were coded in considerable detail with the focus shifting back and forth from the key claims of the participants to the researcher’s

interpretation of the meaning of the responses and subjectively interpreted. Meanwhile, the notes that may be obtained from in-depth interviews may be transcribed immediately. The researcher may be looking for common themes that may be found among the responses to each question. Environmental Triangulation. Triangulation analysis is a tool developed by Margaret Schuler to help advocates perform a strategic analysis of the issues they are working on. The tool examines three aspects: content, structure, and culture. Triangular analysis is a technique for both analyzing and finding answers to a problem, structured around structure, content, and culture in the policy system through transcribing, member checking, and triangulation. The entire interview transcript and add anything

that might have been left out. The information may be shared with the participants in a circle to ensure we interpreted the data correctly using triangulation analysis. The researcher must pos-

2.9. Trustworthiness of the Study—Qualitative research does not claim to be replicable. The researcher purposefully avoids controlling the research conditions and concentrates on recording the complexity of situational contexts and interrelations as they occur naturally (Marshall Rossman, 2006). This study took many extra steps to ensure the results from the data analysis were credible, transferable, dependable, and authentic. *Credibility*. Mertens (2020) defines credibility as a correspondence between the way a participant perceives social constructs and the way the researcher portrays the participant's viewpoints. To ensure credibility in this study, the researcher used persistent observation that allowed for interviews that were long enough to identify salient issues (Mertens, 2020). The researcher also monitored her developing constructions and documented any changes she experienced from the beginning of the study to the end in the analytic memos. This procedure began with the researcher's disclosure of values, beliefs, and experiences that connect her to the topic exploring the perceptions and practices of junior high school teachers towards student-centered learning. *Transferability*. Establishing transferability provides the degree to which the results can be generalized to other situations. The researcher kept an audit trail, which is a meticulous record of the research process so other

researchers can recapture steps and the same conclusions. Extensive and careful descriptions of the time, place, context, and culture of the study were kept developing a thick description (Mertens, 2020). Not only was the data kept, but also the evidence of how the data were reduced, analyzed, and synthesized as well as the process notes that reflect the ongoing inner thoughts, hunches, and reactions of the researcher (Newton Rudestam, 2001). *Conformability*. "Conformability means that the data and the interpretation are not figments of the researcher's imagination" (Mertens, 2005, p. 257). In this study, the data gathered will be analyzed and interpreted properly to arrive at a convincing theme that will further discuss the importance of exploring the perceptions and practices of junior high school teachers toward student-centered learning. To establish conformability, the researcher kept track of the qualitative data so it could be tracked to its source in the interviews. *Authenticity*. To establish authenticity within the study, the researcher presents a balanced view of all perspectives, values, and beliefs. As a researcher, I must avoid bias in gathering the data. This study exploring the perceptions and practices of junior high school teachers towards student-centered learning was use peer debriefing to play the role is asking tough questions about the data collection, data analysis, and data interpretations (Newton Rudestam, 2001).

3. Results and Discussion

This chapter presented the results of the data analysis and the discussion of the results of the study, which focused on exploring the perceptions and practices of junior high school teachers towards student-centered learning was gathered to specifically, this study sought to answer the following questions: What are the teacher's perceptions and practices of junior high school teachers toward student-centered learning. How do teachers explore the practices of junior high school teachers toward student-centered learning? What educational insight and practices can be

drawn from the study? Before I begin my discussion, I would like to establish the symbols I used as I present the quotations based on the responses of the participants of the study. In reference to the transcriptions of the conducted interviews, I used codes to refer to participants of the research question. Their responses were contained and bounded around the three (3) research questions of the study. Moreover, the responses of participants were transcribed in a verbatim manner, translated into English, encoded, and summarized in matrix form, which led to a schema.

3.1. Lived experiences of teachers exploring the perceptions and practices of junior high school teachers towards student-centered learning—

*3.1.1. Adapting pedagogy—*Based on the interview data gathered from the teachers' participants focused on exploring the perceptions and practices of junior high school teachers towards student-centered learning emerged with the theme, of adapting pedagogy. The transcripts of participants of the focus in depth-interview: Answer to the research question and connected to the first theme, which is addressing the adapting pedagogy. Exploring the perceptions and practices addressing the adapting pedagogy, the perceptions and practices of junior high school teachers towards student-centered learning student-centered learning merged with the first theme of adapting pedagogy that was considered in the study. As I analyzed from the narration of other participants based on the perceptions and practices of junior high school teachers towards student-centered learning student-centered learning merged with the first theme of adapting pedagogy that was considered in the study. The statement reflects their participants based on the perceptions and practices of junior high school teachers towards student-centered learning student-centered learning merged with the first theme of adapting pedagogy that was considered in the study. On the other hand, the first objective of this study is the lived experiences of teachers exploring the perceptions and practices of junior high school teachers toward student-centered learning. The study would specifically seek to answer the following queries, emerging

theme adapting pedagogy. As I analyzed from the exploring of the perceptions and practices addressing the adapting pedagogy, the perceptions and practices of junior high school teachers towards student-centered learning student-centered learning merged with the first theme of adapting pedagogy that was considered in the study. Learning is becoming increasingly important in the workforce, where collaboration, problem-solving, and critical thinking are highly valued. By studying and implementing student-centered approaches in junior high school, learners can develop these important skills and become better prepared for success in their future careers. As I analyzed the narration of teacher has a positive outlook and is open to adapting pedagogy to incorporate student-centered learning. They believe it's essential in modern education, indicating a willingness to change their teaching methods to better suit the needs of their students. This is a strong endorsement of the benefits of student-centered learning and adapting pedagogy. This literature review examines the perceptions and practices of junior high school teachers toward student-centered learning in the Philippines. The authors identify factors that influence the adoption of student-centered learning, such as teacher beliefs and attitudes, institutional support, and classroom culture. They also discuss strategies for promoting student-centered learning, including teacher training and support, collaborative learning communities, and addressing the cultural and linguistic diversity of learners (Dacanay and M. R. Marquez, 2021).

*3.1.2. Empowering students—*On the other hand, as I analyzed from the exploring

of the perceptions and practices addressing the adapting pedagogy, the perceptions and practices of junior high school teachers towards student-centered learning student-centered learning. They are making efforts to incorporate more student-centered elements into their teaching, indicating a gradual shift towards adapting their pedagogy, the first objective of this study is the lived experiences of teachers exploring the perceptions and practices of junior high school teachers toward student-centered learning. The study would specifically seek to answer the following queries, emerging theme of empowering students. As I analyzed the narration from the responses stated that empowering students through student-centered learning is a priority for me. However, other responses stated that acknowledge the need for continuous training and support to adapt my pedagogy effectively. It's not just about theory; it's about practical guidance. Empowering students is not just a theme but the foundation of my teaching. Adapting my pedagogy is about fostering independence and critical thinking. Students are more engaged and confident when they have control over their learning. These could include factors such as lack of time, resources, training, or support from the administration. Teacher training and professional development: What kind of training and professional development opportunities are available to junior high school teachers to support the implementation of student-centered learning? Effective time is these opportunities to help teachers to implement these practices (Ghaith, G., Yaghi, H. 2019). As I analyzed the narration this teacher has a positive outlook and is open to exploring the perceptions and practices addressing the adapting pedagogy, the perceptions and practices of junior high school teachers towards student-centered learning student-centered learning. They believe it's essential in modern education, indicating a willingness to change their teaching methods to better suit the needs of their students. This is a

strong endorsement of the benefits of student-centered learning and empowering student. This could include things like project-based learning, inquiry-based learning, or collaborative learning, as well as how these practices are adapted to meet the needs of different subject areas or learning levels (Hvidtfeldt, C., Brinkmann, S. 2019). Support by the ideas of Means, B., Toyama, Y., Murphy, R., Bakia, M., Jones, K. (2020), exploring the perceptions and practices of junior high school teachers towards student-centered learning. adapting pedagogy, empowering students, classroom practices. As I analyzed from the narration of other participants teacher has a positive outlook and is open to adapting pedagogy to incorporate student-centered learning. They are making efforts to incorporate more student-centered elements into their teaching, indicating a gradual shift toward empowering students. Evidence has implicated the prefrontal cortex as a brain region that may be particularly susceptible to the effects of sleep loss, but perplexingly, executive function tasks that putatively measure prefrontal functioning have yielded inconsistent findings within the context of sleep deprivation (Gong, Wang, Xu, Zhong, Peng, Song, Shao, and Weng, 2023). As I analyzed the narration this teacher has a positive outlook and is open to exploring the perceptions and practices addressing the adapting pedagogy, the perceptions, and practices of junior high school teachers towards student-centered learning student-centered learning. Their comments reflect some resistance to adapting pedagogy but an openness to exploring new approaches. This teacher has already integrated student-centered learning into their teaching, which demonstrates a high level of commitment to adapting pedagogy. They highlight the rewards of facilitating student-led learning and emphasize the need to move away from traditional teaching.

3.1.3. Classroom practices—On the other hand, this teacher recognizes the importance

of balance between traditional and student-centered methods. They are adapting their pedagogy by incorporating elements of both approaches, indicating a flexible and pragmatic approach to teaching, the teacher has a positive outlook and is open to exploring the perceptions and practices addressing the adapting pedagogy, the perceptions and practices of junior high school teachers towards student-centered learning student-centered learning addressing the classroom practices. As I analyzed the narration this teacher has a positive outlook and is open to exploring the perceptions and practices addressing the classroom practices, the perceptions, and practices of junior high school teachers towards student-centered learning student-centered learning. They highlight the challenge of finding the right balance between structured and self-directed learning. This teacher is enthusiastic about student-centered learning but seeks training and support to adapt their pedagogy effectively. They recognize the importance of professional development to ensure the successful implementation of student-centered methods. As I analyzed the narration this teacher has a positive outlook and is open to exploring the perceptions and practices addressing the classroom practices, the perceptions, and practices of junior high school teachers towards student-centered learning student-centered learning. They view adapting pedagogy to boost motivation and interest in learning. This teacher believes in the concept of student-centered learning but As I analyzed the narration this teacher has a positive outlook and is open to exploring the perceptions and practices addressing the adapting pedagogy, the perceptions, and practices of junior high school teachers towards student-centered learning student-centered learning. They are adapting their teaching methods while being realistic about the difficulties that may arise. This teacher expresses a desire for additional resources and tools to aid in adapting their ped-

agogy for student-centered learning. They see the potential but recognize the need for support. The researcher would discuss the high school teachers regarding student-centered learning and adapting pedagogy. Teachers range from those who are enthusiastic and experienced with this approach to those who may be more hesitant or in need of additional training and resources. Understanding these perspectives can inform strategies for implementing student-centered learning effectively in junior high schools, including providing the necessary support and resources for classroom practices. As I analyzed the narration some respondents stated that I'm open to the idea of student-centered learning, but it's a bit challenging for me to break away from traditional teaching methods. However, I've started incorporating more group activities and projects where students have some say in what they learn. It's a work in progress Student outcomes: What impact does the implementation of student-centered learning have on student outcomes, such as academic achievement, engagement, motivation, and attitudes towards learning? How do these outcomes compare to more traditional teacher-centered approaches to instruction? School culture and leadership (Harris, M. S., Jones, M. S. 2021). As I analyzed the narration recurring theme in my observations and experiences is the shift from a traditional teacher-centered approach to one that empowers students to take an active role in their learning. It's an approach that requires a fundamental change in mindset. As a teacher, I've found that adapting my pedagogy to align with student-centered learning means relinquishing some control and embracing the idea that my students can and should be co-creators of their education. However, what I've witnessed in my classroom is remarkable. The students, when given the freedom to explore, question, and make decisions about their learning, become more engaged and motivated. They develop a sense of ownership over their education,

Fig. 3. Thematic Framework of teacher’s perceptions and practices of junior high school teachers towards student-centered learning

which in turn fosters critical thinking, problem-solving, and a lifelong love for learning. It’s a rewarding process that not only benefits the students but also renews my passion for teaching. The perceptions and practices of teachers regarding student-centered learning are diverse and dynamic. As a teacher in this context, I’ve come to realize that this pedagogical approach is not a one-size-fits-all solution but rather a transformative journey of exploration and adaptation. Teachers’ perceptions and practices of student-centered learning in junior high schools in the Philippines: a systematic review” by R. B. Pascual, S. L. P. Castillo, R. A. C. Rodriguez (2021). This review synthesizes the findings of studies on teachers’ perceptions and practices of student-centered learning in the Philippines. The authors highlight the importance of teacher training and professional development in promoting student-centered approaches and identify gaps in current research. Another aspect that has struck me is the importance of inclusivity and catering to the diverse needs of students. Adapting my pedagogy means recognizing that each student is unique, and their learning styles

vary. As I embrace student-centered learning, I’ve learned to adjust my approach to ensure that no student is left behind. It’s about providing opportunities for every student to thrive, regardless of their background or abilities. In this journey, I’ve come to understand the significance of collaboration. Student-centered learning often fosters a sense of community within the classroom. Students work together, share ideas, and take charge of their learning as a group. It’s a beautiful outcome of this pedagogical approach. The world is changing rapidly, and education must adapt to prepare students for the challenges and opportunities of the 21st century. Adapting pedagogy to empower students through student-centered learning is a significant step in this direction. It’s not a one-time adjustment but an ongoing process of growth and evolution as an educator. While challenges exist, the rewards are immense, and the impact on students is lasting. It’s a journey that I, as a junior high school teacher, am committed to and passionate about, as it empowers the future leaders and thinkers of tomorrow.

3.2. *Teachers explore the practices of junior high school teachers toward student-centered learning*—The second objective of this

study is the teachers explore the practices of junior high school teachers toward student-centered learning, considering the three major

themes such as: Balancing Traditions, Innovation, Classroom culture, and management. Based on the interview data gathered from the teacher's coping mechanism with the challenges teachers explore the practices of junior high school teachers towards student-centered learning, considering the three major themes such as: Balancing Traditions, Innovation, Classroom culture, and management. Therefore, based on the research questions the study dealt with the teacher's coping mechanism with the challenges in teachers exploring the practices of junior high school teachers towards student-centered learning, considering the theme Balancing Traditions.

3.2.1. Balancing Traditions—As I analyzed the narration of challenges in teachers exploring the practices of junior high school teachers towards student-centered learning, considering the theme of balancing traditions. One of the biggest challenges is that student readiness for student-centered learning varies widely. Some students adapt quickly and thrive, while others struggle with the newfound freedom. We must tailor our teaching to accommodate these differences, which can be complex. Balancing traditions while preparing students for these tests can be a delicate act. We worry that student-centered learning might not align perfectly with test prep. I analyzed the narration of challenges in teachers exploring the practices of junior high school teachers towards student-centered learning, considering the theme of balancing traditions that adopting student-centered learning means we must rethink how we assess and evaluate students. It's a challenge to develop assessments that accurately gauge their progress and mastery of content without relying solely on traditional exams. Based on the interview data gathered from the teacher's coping mechanism with the challenges teachers explore the practices of junior high school teachers towards student-centered learning, considering the three major themes such as: Balancing Traditions, In-

novation, Classroom culture, and management. Many teachers are enthusiastic about adopting student-centered approaches, but there's often a lack of proper training and resources to support this shift. I analyzed the narration of challenges in teachers exploring the practices of junior high school teachers towards student-centered learning, considering the theme of balancing traditions of the biggest challenges in implementing student-centered learning is the pressure to cover a fixed curriculum. Traditional teaching methods are often seen as more aligned with standardized testing and curriculum requirements. Balancing the need for content coverage with student-centered practices can be quite demanding.

3.2.2. Innovation—On the other hand, It's a challenge to develop assessments that accurately gauge their progress and mastery of content without relying solely on traditional exams. Based on the interview data gathered from the teacher's coping mechanism with the challenges teachers explore the practices of junior high school teachers towards student-centered learning, considering the three major themes such as: Innovation, not all colleagues are on board with student-centered learning. Resistance from some teachers who prefer traditional methods can create a hostile work environment and make it more challenging to implement these changes. Students have varying levels of readiness for student-centered learning. While some adapt quickly and thrive, others find it difficult to adjust to the change in teaching style. Balancing the needs of all students while implementing these new methods is a complex task. I analyzed the narration often involves preparing students for standardized tests. There's a constant struggle between aligning teaching methods with these tests and the desire to adopt more student-centered approaches. Balancing these two aspects is a significant challenge. I analyzed that the narration curriculum is packed, and there's often a sense of urgency to cover

material. Balancing traditions while integrating student-centered practices without falling behind can be a constant struggle. Not all teachers are on the same page when it comes to student-centered learning. Some of my colleagues are more comfortable with traditional methods, and there can be resistance to change. It can be challenging to coordinate and align our teaching approaches. I analyzed the narration Junior high school teachers often face the challenge of aligning student-centered practices with the mandated curriculum. Balancing the desire to encourage self-directed learning with meeting standardized testing requirements is a delicate act. One of the biggest hurdles is the lack of training and resources for implementing student-centered practices. Without proper guidance, it's challenging to make the transition and create effective, engaging lessons that empower students.

3.2.3. Classroom Culture and Management—On the other hand, these responses from participants underscore the difficulties teachers face when attempting to balance traditional teaching methods with student-centered learning in junior high schools. It highlights the need for ongoing professional development, adequate resources, and support to make this transition more manageable. I analyzed the narration of students entering the classroom with varying levels of readiness for student-centered learning. Some adapt quickly, while others struggle with the shift. It's a constant challenge to tailor our teaching to meet the diverse needs of the students. Based on this statement, I analyzed the narration on the other hand, these responses from participants underscore the difficulties teachers face when attempting to balance traditional teaching methods with student-centered learning in junior high schools. It highlights the need for ongoing professional development, adequate resources, and support to make this transition more manageable. I analyzed the narration's fixed expectations about

how education should be delivered, based on their own experiences. Convincing them of the merits of student-centered learning while honoring their expectations can be a considerable challenge. Adapting assessment and grading practices to align with student-centered learning is a constant challenge. Finding ways to assess students effectively without relying solely on traditional exams is a process that can be time-consuming. I analyzed the narration for teachers, transitioning from a traditional mindset to one that embraces student-centered learning is a significant challenge. It requires a change in the role they traditionally played, from the 'sage on the stage' to the 'guide on the side. These responses from participants underscore the difficulties teachers face when attempting to balance traditional teaching methods with student-centered learning in junior high schools. It highlights the need for ongoing professional development, adequate resources, and support to make this transition more manageable. Shifting from a traditional teaching mindset to one that embraces student-centered learning requires significant adjustment. It's challenging for educators to let go of the traditional authoritative role and embrace a more facilitating role. Balancing traditions with student-centered learning can be time-intensive. The time to design and implement engaging, student-centered activities can be a constant challenge, particularly with other responsibilities and time constraints. Shifting from a traditional teaching mindset to one that embraces student-centered learning requires significant adjustment. It's challenging for educators to let go of the traditional authoritative role and embrace a more facilitating role Classroom Practices: How do teachers learn about student-centered learning practices and how do they implement these practices in their classrooms. A study by Greenberg and Cheryan (2021) found that teacher training programs that incorporate active learning and collaborative problem-solving can support

Fig. 4. Teachers Coping the challenges in the practices of junior high school teachers toward student-centered learning

the development of student-centered teaching practices. Parent and community involvement: How do teachers involve parents and the community in student-centered learning practices, and what are the benefits and challenges of this involvement. A study by Yang et al. (2021) found that involving parents and the community in student-centered learning practices can improve student outcomes and promote positive

relationships between schools and the community. I analyzed the narration on the other hand, these responses from participants underscore the difficulties teachers face when attempting to balance traditional teaching methods with student-centered learning in junior high schools. It highlights the need for ongoing professional development, adequate resources, and support to make this transition more manageable.

3.3. *To explore the perceptions and practices of junior high school teachers toward student-centered learning*—The third objective of this study is to explore the perceptions and practices of junior high school teachers toward student-centered learning. The study would specifically seek to answer the queries, of what educational insight and practices can be drawn from the study findings of the study having emerged major themes such as student engagement and motivation, teacher-centered to student-centered, and Collaboration and peer learning.

such as: Innovation, not all colleagues are on board with student-centered learning. Resistance from some teachers who prefer traditional methods can create a hostile work environment and make it more challenging for student engagement and motivation. As I analyzed the narration of responses reflect the various challenges teachers encounter when trying to strike a balance between traditional teaching methods and student-centered learning in junior high schools. It underscores the need for support, resources, and professional development to facilitate this transition effectively. Teacher training and professional development are key factors in promoting student-centered approaches, and there is a need for further research to identify effective strategies for supporting teachers in this area, while also promoting effective strategies for supporting teachers and promot-

3.3.1. *Student engagement and motivation*—Based on the interview data gathered from the teacher’s coping mechanism with the challenges teachers explore the practices of junior high school teachers towards student-centered learning, considering the three major themes

ing student participation and engagement in the learning process. As I analyzed the narration of the study teachers, transitioning from a traditional mindset to one that embraces student-centered learning is a significant challenge by Harasim et al. (2021) found that technology can support student-centered learning practices, but it is important to consider issues such as accessibility and equity. Culturally responsive teaching: How do teachers incorporate culturally responsive teaching practices into student-centered learning, and how do these practices support student engagement and achievement. As I analyzed the narration of balancing traditions with student-centered learning can be challenging due to the constraints of a packed curriculum. There's often pressure to cover specific content, making it difficult to allocate time for student-centered activities. Not all teachers are equally receptive to the idea of student-centered learning. The resistance from colleagues who prefer traditional methods can create tension and make it challenging to align teaching approaches within a school.

3.3.2. Teacher-centered to student-centered—On the other hand, they explore the perceptions and practices of junior high school teachers toward student-centered learning. Some students adapt seamlessly, while others may struggle with the shift. Teachers need to adapt their approach to cater to these differences. explore the perceptions and practices of junior high school teachers toward student-centered learning. Finding alternative ways to assess students' progress without relying heavily on traditional exams can be teacher-centered to student-centered. As I analyzed the narration they explored the perceptions and practices of junior high school teachers toward student-centered learning. Some students adapt seamlessly, while others may struggle with the shift. a major obstacle is the lack of training and resources to effectively implement student-centered learning. Without the proper guidance

and tools, it's challenging to make a successful transition. Having the necessary support from school administrators is crucial for the successful implementation of student-centered practices. A lack of backing from higher-ups can make it more challenging to balance traditions with innovative methods. As I analyzed the narration they explored the perceptions and practices of junior high school teachers toward student-centered learning. Some students adapt seamlessly, while others may struggle with the shift. shifting from a traditional teaching mindset to one that embraces student-centered learning requires significant adjustment. It's challenging for educators to let go of the traditional authoritative role and embrace a more facilitating role. As I analyzed the narration of these responses provided insight into the challenges faced by teachers as they attempt to navigate the balance between traditional teaching methods and student-centered learning in junior high schools. It underscores the need for professional development, resources, and support to facilitate a successful transition. As I analyzed the narration balancing traditions with student-centered learning can be time-intensive. Finding the time to design and implement engaging student-centered activities can be challenging, especially with other demands on teachers' time. Transitioning from a traditional teaching mindset to one that embraces student-centered learning requires a significant shift. Teachers must move from being the 'sage on the stage' to the 'guide on the side,' which can be challenging. Having strong administrative support is crucial for the successful implementation of student-centered practices. A lack of support from school administrators can hinder efforts to balance traditions with innovative methods.

3.3.3. Collaboration and peer learning—On the other hand, they explore the perceptions and practices of junior high school teachers toward student-centered learning. Some students adapt seamlessly while others may struggle with

the shift they explored the perceptions and practices of junior high school teachers toward Collaboration and peer learning. As I analyzed the narration explored the perceptions and practices of junior high school teachers toward student-centered learning shifting to student-centered learning often requires a reevaluation of grading and assessment methods. Teachers need to find alternative ways to assess student progress without solely relying on traditional exams, which can be time-consuming. Navigating parental expectations rooted in their own traditional educational experiences can be a real challenge. Convincing parents of the advantages of student-centered learning while addressing their concerns is an ongoing effort. Collaboration and peer learning, they explore the perceptions and practices of junior high school teachers toward student-centered learning. Some students adapt seamlessly while others may struggle with the shift they explored the perceptions and practices of junior high school teachers toward Collaboration and peer learning. Based on this statement, I analyzed the narration of others having strong administrative support is crucial for the successful implementation of student-centered practices. A lack of support from school administrators can hinder efforts to balance traditions with innovative methods, traditions with student-centered learning can be time-intensive. Finding the time to design and implement engaging student-centered activities can be challenging, especially with other demands on teachers' time. As I analyzed the narration of these responses provided insight into the challenges faced by teachers as they attempt to navigate the balance between traditional teaching methods and student-centered learning in junior high schools. It underscores the need for professional development, resources, and support to facilitate a successful transition. As I analyzed the narration one of the most significant challenges is the resistance from fellow teachers who are more inclined towards traditional methods. Achiev-

ing alignment and cooperation among educators within a school can be quite a hurdle. Junior high schools often focus on preparing students for standardized tests, which can sometimes be at odds with the principles of student-centered learning. Many teachers acknowledge the benefits of student-centered learning but find it challenging to implement due to a lack of proper training and resources. Without adequate support, the transition can be difficult, exploring the perceptions and practices of junior high school teachers towards student-centered learning. adapting pedagogy, empowering students, classroom practices, balancing traditions, innovation, classroom culture, and management, and for objective number 3 exploring the perceptions and practices of junior high school teachers towards student-centered learning merged with themes such as student engagement and motivation, Student engagement and motivation, teacher-centered to student-centered, and Collaboration and peer learning. As I analyzed the narration of A notable challenge is the significant variation in student readiness for student-centered learning. Some students embrace the shift with ease, while others struggle to adapt. This necessitates a flexible teaching approach. How can curriculum design and implementation support student-centered learning practices, and what are the challenges and opportunities of this approach? A study by Escobar-Cedano et al. (2021) found that a competency-based curriculum design supported the implementation of student-centered learning practices. How can parents and community members be involved in supporting student-centered learning practices, and what are the benefits and challenges of this approach? A study by Gao et al. (2021) found that parent and community involvement can support student-centered learning practices, but that communication and collaboration must be established to ensure a shared understanding of these practices.

Fig. 5. Educational management insights drawn from the study

4. Implications and Future Directions

Presented in this chapter was a brief overview of the study followed by implications based on the findings of the study. Future directions in the field of culturally responsive teachers through the lens of classroom advisers were also discussed here. The target participants for this study were composed of twelve (12) participants from the line-up of public junior high school faculty, who were still teaching during the school year 2022-2023. The respondents would join for an in-depth interview (IDI). The researcher considered the faculty from selected public schools who are still teaching. From this population, a sample of twelve (12) junior high school teachers was purposefully selected. The study was to explore what are the teacher’s perceptions and practices of junior high school teachers toward student-centered learning. How do teachers explore the practices of junior high school teachers toward student-centered learning and What educational insight and practices can be drawn from the study.

4.1. Findings—The findings revealed that the Exploring the perceptions and practices of junior high school teachers towards student-centered learning. Teacher’s perceptions and practices of junior high school teachers towards student-centered learning and the emergence of common themes: adapting pedagogy, empowering students, and in limited meaningful classroom practices. It was important to challenges yourself and create an active environment in your classroom to apply pedagogy. You have to work on changing the overall environment of your classroom to implement the pedagogy. Limited meaningful classroom practices were the of stress and time management. However, it totally negative perse because teachers could create and shift negative to positive environment. The merged themes with were student engagement and motivation, student engagement and motivation, teacher-centered to student-centered, and collaboration and peer learning. Students who are motivated in their learning are going to show characteristics of being goal-oriented and are likely to see more success and higher achievement. Motivated learners take responsibility and initiative, show curiosity and a willingness to try, put forth genuine effort, and take pride in their work. While, any teachers strive to implement a blend of teacher-centered and student-centered learning styles sometimes within the same classroom — based on their own instincts, research and experience. The student-centered approach to education also has relevance for teachers who choose to de-

velop a deeper understanding of the art and science of education by pursuing a master's degree. The teachers' coping mechanisms by considering the three major themes: balancing traditions, innovation, and support from colleagues, effective classroom culture, and management. The key is not just to adapt to change but to do so in a way that respects and revitalizes the traditions that have made the company unique and successful. In navigating this balance, organizations can forge a future that honors their past while embracing the new possibilities that innovation brings. To apply the right balance between tradition and innovation, it was essential to consider the benefits and drawbacks of each and choose the right technologies. Moreover, it was important to consider the human factor and involve stakeholders in the decision-making process. Innovation was observed however, not all colleagues were on board with student-centered learning. Resistance from some teachers who prefer traditional methods can create a hostile work environment and make it more challenging for student engagement and motivation. The educational management insight was drawn from the study and having emerged three themes such as student engagement and motivation, teacher-centered to student-centered, and collaboration and peer learning. Engaging students in the learning process increases their attention and focus and moves them to more critical thinking. Instructors who adopt a student-centered approach to instruction increase opportunities for student engagement, which then helps everyone more successfully achieve the course's learning objectives. While, it has been observed that teacher collaboration is a critical component that can improve educational accomplishments. By pooling their knowledge, expertise, and resources, educators may create cutting-edge teaching methods that raise student engagement, success, and achievement.

4.1.1. Implications—The results of my analysis revealed the following significant find-

ings. The findings revealed that the exploring the perceptions and practices of junior high school teachers towards student-centered learning. Teacher's perceptions and practices of junior high school teachers towards student-centered learning and the emergence of common themes: adapting pedagogy, empowering students, and in limited meaningful classroom practices. The teachers' coping mechanisms by considering the three major themes: balancing traditions, innovation, and support from colleagues, effective classroom culture, and management, it was essential to consider the benefits and drawbacks of each and choose the right technologies. Moreover, it was important to consider the human factor and involve stakeholders in the decision-making process. Innovation was observed however, not all colleagues were on board with student-centered learning. Resistance from some teachers who prefer traditional methods can create a hostile work environment and make it more challenging for student engagement and motivation. The educational management insight was drawn from the study and having emerged three themes such as student engagement and motivation, teacher-centered to student-centered, and collaboration and peer learning. Engaging students in the learning process increases their attention and focus and moves them to more critical thinking. Teachers need more opportunities for professional development in the realm of student-centered learning. Implications suggest that investing in training programs and resources is essential to help educators effectively navigate these challenges. Teachers may benefit from professional development and training on recognizing and addressing sleep-related issues. Future Directions These responses highlight the potential future directions and actions that can help teachers address the challenges of balancing traditions with student-centered learning in junior high schools. They emphasize the need for innovation, support, and a collaborative ap-

proach to create a more effective educational environment. As a future direction, we should explore innovative curriculum design that allows for a more seamless integration of student-centered learning. This might involve reevaluating the existing curriculum to create space for more flexible teaching methods. Future directions should involve more active engagement with the community and parents. We need to inform them about the benefits of student-centered learning and how it aligns with modern education. This can help bridge the gap in expectations. To balance traditions with student-centered learning, future directions might involve the development of hybrid teaching approaches. These approaches can integrate the best of both worlds and address the pressure of standardized testing. In the future, we should explore and implement more flexible assessment models that align with student-centered practices. This may require a shift away from traditional exams and a focus on alternative ways of evaluating student progress. Future directions should include changes in administrative policies to provide stronger support for teachers. School leaders should champion student-centered learning, allocate resources, and implement policies that encourage a more balanced approach. We should encourage research into the effectiveness of student-centered learning in junior high schools. Future directions should involve data-driven decision-making to assess the impact of these practices and guide further improvements. Future directions should encourage mentorship and collaboration among teachers. Experienced teachers can guide those who are new to student-centered practices, creating a supportive environment for growth and development. To address challenges, future directions should involve customized teacher training programs. Not all teachers face the same obstacles, and personalized training can help them overcome their specific challenges. These responses highlight the potential future directions

and actions that can help teachers address the challenges of balancing traditions with student-centered learning in junior high schools. They emphasize the need for innovation, support, and a collaborative approach to create a more effective educational environment.

4.1.2. Future Directions—These responses highlight the potential future directions and actions that can help teachers address the challenges of balancing traditions with student-centered learning in junior high schools. They emphasize the need for innovation, support, and a collaborative approach to create a more effective educational environment. As a future direction, we should explore innovative curriculum design that allows for a more seamless integration of student-centered learning. This might involve reevaluating the existing curriculum to create space for more flexible teaching methods. Future directions should involve more active engagement with the community and parents. We need to inform them about the benefits of student-centered learning and how it aligns with modern education. This can help bridge the gap in expectations. To balance traditions with student-centered learning, future directions might involve the development of hybrid teaching approaches. These approaches can integrate the best of both worlds and address the pressure of standardized testing. In the future, we should explore and implement more flexible assessment models that align with student-centered practices. This may require a shift away from traditional exams and a focus on alternative ways of evaluating student progress. Future directions should include changes in administrative policies to provide stronger support for teachers. School leaders should champion student-centered learning, allocate resources, and implement policies that encourage a more balanced approach. We should encourage research into the effectiveness of student-centered learning in junior high schools. Future directions should involve data-

driven decision-making to assess the impact of these practices and guide further improvements. Future directions should encourage mentorship and collaboration among teachers. Experienced teachers can guide those who are new to student-centered practices, creating a supportive environment for growth and development. To address challenges, future directions should involve customized teacher training programs. Not all teachers face the same obstacles, and personalized training can help them overcome their specific challenges. These responses highlight the potential future directions and actions that can help teachers address the challenges of balancing traditions with student-centered learning in junior high schools. They emphasize the need for innovation, support, and a collaborative approach to create a more effective educational environment.

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